

Telemedicine in Neurological Healthcare

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Abstract

Background: Telemedicine has become an integral part of modern healthcare, particularly in addressing the growing demand for neurological services. Neurological conditions, such as stroke, epilepsy, multiple sclerosis, and Parkinson's disease, often require specialized care that can be challenging to access, especially in underserved or remote areas. Telemedicine offers innovative solutions to bridge this gap.

Objective: This paper examines the opportunities and challenges associated with the adoption of telemedicine in neurological healthcare, focusing on its impact on accessibility, diagnostic accuracy, and patient outcomes.

Methods: A comprehensive review of current telemedicine practices in neurology was conducted, including the integration of advanced technologies such as wearable devices, remote monitoring tools, and artificial intelligence. Barriers to implementation, including technological, regulatory, and equity-related challenges, were also analyzed.

Results: Telemedicine has demonstrated significant benefits, such as improved access to care, enhanced patient monitoring, and reduced healthcare disparities. However, limitations such as the reliance on stable internet infrastructure, potential data privacy risks, and the difficulty of replicating physical neurological examinations in a virtual setting remain critical challenges.

Conclusions: Telemedicine has the potential to revolutionize neurological healthcare by making specialized care more accessible and efficient. Addressing challenges related to infrastructure, regulatory compliance, and equitable access is essential for maximizing its benefits. Future research and policy development should focus on creating robust frameworks for the sustainable integration of telemedicine into neurological practice.

Keywords

Telemedicine , Neurology , healthcare